

Mini tutorial to create a CS project using Epicollect5 and Zooniverse

Lifecycle-aware citizen science templates

In this guideline, we are going to show how to create a system in ACTION to collect and process data using two external tools Epicollect5¹ and Zooniverse. To illustrate this process, we will use the example of street spectra, one of our pilots.

The StreetSpectra project wishes to turn the smartphones into scientific instruments to analyze lamps colors and their spectra. More information about this project, together with an extensive tutorial, can be found in D2.1 - Tutorial of street spectra project.

The next picture depicts the architecture of the system.

In this pilot, we have identified two use cases: i) volunteers will take the spectrum from a particular lamppost using the camera of its mobile phone and ii) volunteers will classify the spectra taken in the previous use case.

To connect both systems, a script has been developed to export the images (and metadata) taken with Epicollect to the Zooniverse platform, adding them as tasks in the Subject Set section. Note that this script has been deployed for this first version, in later versions, it will be part of the Data Management executor described in Section 3.3.

First, we are going to describe how to create a project in Epicollect to locate and to store spectrum from lampposts. Epicollect is a platform to allow users to create and easily design web forms to collect data.

¹ <https://five.epicollect.net/>

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Steps

1. Identify the data you want to collect. In our case we have identify the following data needed for this project (datetime, location, image, additional observations)
2. Log in the platform (<https://five.epicollect.net/login>). Epicollect uses google authentication as a login authentication system. For that reason, you will need a google account to create projects.
3. Once you enter into the platform, you will see a create project option in the menu. You will have to provide some extra information about your projects such as project name, small description and a name for the form. The name of your project must be unique in the system because it will be used as an identifier.

4. Once the project is created, you can start to build your form. For that, select the option FORM BUILDER.

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5. A set of fields will appear in the left side menu. Most of them are the typical fields in web forms such as Text, radio, dropdown and checkbox fields. But there are other interesting components to get location, current date or upload photos. Each component in the form will be shown to the volunteer as a new window.

6. To add a field in the form, you have to drag and drop each component you need to the form (in the central part of the page) and configure it in the right side area.
7. The first component is a text area that will show a welcome message to the volunteer.

8. We need our application to get the nick of the volunteer. For that, you have to drag and drop the Text Box component, analog to the input field in web forms. To configure this component, we have to write the question that the application will do to the volunteers. In the advanced option, we can define a regular expression to validate the answer although it is not going to be used in our example.

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9. Following the data identified in the first step, the project needs the datetime of the observation. We will use two special fields: date and time. In the **Advanced** option we can define the date and time format. One interesting characteristic of these fields is that can be automatically fill in with the current date and time when it is shown to the volunteer.

10. The next information we need is the location of the lamppost. For that, we will use the component Location. Similar to the date field, volunteers will not have to introduce the location, it can be taken automatically from the mobile.
11. Next important data is an image of the lamppost spectrum. We will select the image component. This component allows users to take images from the mobile camera or from the user's gallery. This image will be uploaded to the Epicollect servers.

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12. Lastly, we will use a Text Box component to allow volunteers to write some relevant additional observations about the spectrum taken.
13. Once the form is complete, it can be saved by clicking on the *Save Project* button.
14. Finally, we need to publish the project so it can be listed and used with the application of epicollect. Go to the home page and configure these options: Access -> Public, Status -> Active and Visibility -> Hidden

ACTION STREET SPECTRA

Project homepage: <https://five.epicollect.net/project/action-street-spectra>

The entire example can be found here: <https://five.epicollect.net/project/action-street-spectra>

All the collected information is openly available² to all users and can be downloaded in CSV or JSON format. Also, can be consulted in table format as can be seen in the following figure.

² <https://five.epicollect.net/project/action-street-spectra/data>

ACTION STREET SPECTRA... street_spectra ▾

 Download Table Map Exit

Total: 436, 1/9 < >

Filter by title

FROM: 02 SEP, 19 TO: 30 DEC, 19 NEWEST ▾ X

View	Title	Created At	Time	Location	Take an image of a lamppost	Observations
	5cdc9541-9039-4461-...	30th Dec, 2019	20:08:29	40.616933, 20.78072		Korçë, Albania
	0ada66cd-144a-4f56-...	29th Dec, 2019	18:40:47	40.357391, -3.783624		
	6397bbf-5355-4052-9...	28th Dec, 2019	21:03:20	39.484582, -0.359485		LED muy blancos tipo mazorca.
	3b2aa76d-5381-4607-...	27th Dec, 2019	16:54:29	41.329733, 19.824692		Tirana, Albania
	60073dbf-bd09-4195-...	26th Dec, 2019	20:22:29	40.13082, -5.460953		
	1938f289-27ea-4009-...	25th Dec, 2019	19:58:37	40.354852, -3.813737		
	1c689b0e-2967-45a0-...	25th Dec, 2019	19:55:45	40.354557, -3.815465		
	6c4ee5dc-75ef-48a3-...	25th Dec, 2019	19:48:53	40.353809, -3.808964		

Fig XXX. StreetSpectra application in Epicollect

If you remember the second use case, the objective of our project in Zooniverse is to classify the images collected by users in epicollect5.

Steps

1. You have to sign up on the Zooniverse platform. In this case, the platform doesn't allow the use of the google authentication system.
2. Sign in the platform with the credentials used in the registration process.
3. Once you are in the platform, you can start to work in a project clicking in the BUILD A PROJECT option of the menu

4. In the new window, you will have to set up the details of your project. It includes name, description, introduction and tags to make your project findable in the zooniverse platform.

5. After that, we have to build a small tutorial to help volunteers to classify the images collected by Epicollect. First click in the *Tutorial* option (1) and write a name for your tutorial (2). You can add steps in the tutorial clicking in the Add a step button (3). Each step is composed by a text with images that can be configured in an online editor (4). After you have added all the steps, you can build the tutorial (5). The tutorial will be associated to an specific workflow.

6. Once the tutorial is completed, we start to define the workflow. In our case, we are going to create only one workflow. You will have to click in New Workflow button (2) and a new entry will appear in the workflow list component (3)

- In this one workflow, we will create one task for selecting a region of interest (which includes the lamppost and the spectrum). You will select the *drawing* template. Also, you have to select in the *Choices section* a rectangle as a type of marker.

- Now, we are going to create another task to classify the spectrum. We will have to repeat the process but in this case, we have to select the *question* template.
- Once the second task is created, we have to connect both tasks. So you have to come back to the first task and adding the second task as a Next task to be executed.

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10. Now, we have defined a workflow with the necessary tasks to classify the spectra. Next step is to feed the system with the images produced by the epicollect. This can be done manually in the subject sets section or automatically with the future tool of ACTION to manage workflows (see section 3.3)
11. The application is ready and can be published in the visibility section.

The application is available in:

<https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/actionprojecteu/street-spectra>

In this first version, we have created a python script to feed the system with images. In later version, this script will be integrated into the data management executor tool. As an example, the following picture depicts the schema of the process.

Fig XXX. StreetSpectra application in Epicollect